

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SPEECH CULTURE IN MEDIA DISCOURSE

Turayeva Diyora Ixtiyorovna

Department of english language and literature, teacher, National University of Uzbekistan,
Tashkent

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Abstract. This article explores the multifaceted importance of speech culture in media discourse, examining its impact on communication effectiveness, audience perception, and societal cohesion. By fostering a culture of respectful and inclusive language use, media outlets can enhance their credibility, promote dialogue across diverse perspectives, and contribute to a more informed and empathetic public discourse.

Keywords: speech culture, media discourse, digital media, media content, traditional speech norms, digital landscape

Аннотация. В этой статье исследуется многогранное значение культуры речи в медиадискурсе, изучается ее влияние на эффективность коммуникации, восприятие аудитории и сплоченность общества. Развивая культуру уважительного и инклюзивного использования языка, средства массовой информации могут повысить свой авторитет, способствовать диалогу с учетом различных точек зрения и способствовать более информированному и чуткому общественному дискурсу.

Ключевые слова: речевая культура, медиадискурс, цифровые медиа, медиаконтент, традиционные речевые нормы, цифровой ландшафт.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ommaviy axborot vositalarida nutq madaniyatining ko'p qirrali ahamiyatini o'rganadi, uning muloqot samaradorligi, auditoriyani idrok etish va jamiyat birligiga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Tildan hurmatli va inklyuziv foydalanish madaniyatini rivojlantirish orqali ommaviy axborot vositalari o'z ishonchini oshirishi, turli nuqtai nazarlar bo'yicha muloqotni rivojlantirishi va ko'proq xabardor va empatik jamoatchilik nutqiga hissa qo'shishi mumkinligi haqida so'z boradi

Kalit so'zlar: nutq madaniyati, media-diskurs, raqamli media, media-kontent, an'anaviy nutq normalari, raqamli landshaft.

INTRODUCTION

In the vast expanse of media discourse, the concept of speech culture serves as both a foundation and a guiding principle. Speech culture encompasses the norms, values, and practices governing how language is used in communication. Within media discourse, it shapes not only the content but also the manner in which messages are conveyed, received, and interpreted by the public. This article delves into the critical role of speech culture in media, exploring its influence across different media formats and highlighting its enduring significance in an ever-evolving digital landscape.

The role of speech culture in media discourse is a linchpin in shaping how information is conveyed and interpreted across various platforms. Speech culture comprises the ethical standards, linguistic norms, and communicative practices that govern language use, significantly influencing media's capacity to inform, persuade, and engage audiences. In media discourse, it ensures that language is not only used responsibly but also reflects a sensitivity to the audience's diversity and the content's impact on societal norms and values.

In the era of digital media, speech culture faces new challenges and opportunities. The rapid exchange of information and the blending of formal and informal communication have

transformed traditional speech norms, requiring a dynamic and adaptable approach to media discourse. This evolution is a double-edged sword; while it fosters more open and accessible communication, it also raises concerns about the dilution of language standards and the proliferation of misinformation.

Speech culture in media discourse plays a crucial role in upholding the integrity of public dialogue. It sets the tone for respectful and constructive discourse, influencing public opinion and contributing to a well-informed society. Media professionals bear a significant responsibility in this regard, as their adherence to speech culture principles can enhance the quality and credibility of media content [1].

Addressing the complexities of speech culture in today's media landscape requires a collaborative effort among media practitioners, regulatory bodies, and audiences. By committing to high standards of speech culture, media can navigate the challenges of digital communication while maintaining its critical role in society. Ultimately, the continued evolution of speech culture in media discourse underscores the importance of ethical communication in fostering an informed, respectful, and engaged public dialogue [2].

The new media have caught on for a reason. Knowledge is increasing exponentially; human brainpower and waking hours are not. Fortunately, the Internet and information technologies are helping us manage, search and retrieve our collective intellectual output at different scales

No less significant is the next parameter — the media channel that carries the text to mass audience. Since the famous statement by Marshall McLuhan “the medium is the message” the huge impact of technological or media component proper on the information distributed through means of mass communication has been recognized by all media scholars. Each media channel — the press, radio, television and the Internet, is characterized by a certain set of media qualities, determined by the technology used and the nature of this or that media itself. These media qualities play crucial role in shaping concrete media texts, which by definition, are based on integral unity of verbal and media components[3].

A great significance for media linguistics’ theory represents a statement concerning mechanisms of texts perception, that runs as follows: “correctness of text perception is determined not only by the choice of language units and their cohesion, but also relies on the shared background knowledge, or *communicative context*”. When applied to mass communication the concept of communicative context is primarily understood as the whole set of conditions and prerequisites involved in media text production, transmission and perception, in other words, the sum total of all extralinguistic factors⁴ standing behind the verbal part of a media text. Hence the concept of communicative context includes a wide range of phenomena: from socially and culturally determined reconstruction of events and politically biased interpretations to the category of ideological modality, the notion of meta-message and the whole spectrum of factors that influence the perception of media consumers. Thus, the concept of communicative context becomes closely linked with the general concept of discourse, integrating all components of a text as a final product of human communication: verbal part proper and nonverbal, including the whole variety of social, cultural, situational and contextual factors[4].

Mass media language comprises all the texts created and delivered by Mass media. Mass media language is the inner language system characterized by the specific linguastylistic features. Mass media language is considered as the unique sign system of combined character with the definite correlation of verbal and audio-visual components peculiar to press, radio, Tv, internet.

Media speech as the basic unit of mass media culture is the complex multilevel system based on such main categories as being media, mass, integritiveness and openness.

Speech culture encompasses the language, tone, and style used in communication, particularly within media platforms. It influences how messages are perceived and interpreted by audiences, shaping public opinion and societal norms. In the context of media discourse, speech culture plays a crucial role in several key areas[5]:

1. Communication Effectiveness: The way information is conveyed impacts its reception and understanding. A positive speech culture characterized by clarity, accuracy, and empathy enhances communication effectiveness, ensuring that messages resonate with diverse audiences.

2. Audience Perception: The language used in media discourse shapes audience perceptions of issues, individuals, and events. A respectful and inclusive speech culture fosters trust and credibility, while inflammatory or divisive rhetoric can erode public trust and exacerbate social tensions.

3. Societal Cohesion: Media discourse influences societal cohesion by either fostering unity or exacerbating divisions. A speech culture that promotes dialogue, empathy, and understanding across diverse perspectives contributes to social cohesion and harmony.

4. Narrative Shaping: Media outlets have the power to shape narratives and agendas through their language choices. By adhering to ethical speech practices and avoiding sensationalism or bias, media practitioners can uphold the integrity of their reporting and promote a more balanced public discourse.

5. Conflict Mediation: In situations of conflict or controversy, speech culture can either escalate tensions or facilitate resolution. Media outlets have a responsibility to engage in constructive dialogue, refrain from incendiary language, and provide a platform for diverse voices to be heard.

6. Sense of Belonging: A supportive and inclusive speech culture fosters a sense of belonging within communities, ensuring that all individuals feel valued and represented in media discourse.

Speech culture manifests uniquely across various media formats, each presenting distinct challenges and opportunities for the conveyance of language and ideas. In traditional media such as television and radio, speech culture emphasizes clarity, eloquence, and a degree of formality. These formats require a careful balance between engaging the audience and maintaining professional standards of communication, given their wide and diverse audience reach. The immediacy and auditory nature of these media demand precision in language use, ensuring messages are accessible and resonant with viewers and listeners of varied backgrounds.

Print media, including newspapers and magazines, upholds a rigorous standard of speech culture characterized by meticulous attention to language, accuracy, and integrity. The permanence of the printed word necessitates a high level of responsibility in reporting and commentary, with a strong emphasis on thorough fact-checking and adherence to journalistic ethics. The structured nature of print media allows for in-depth analysis and nuanced discussion, reinforcing its role in fostering an informed public discourse.

Conversely, online platforms and social media represent a dynamic frontier where speech culture is continually negotiated and redefined. The digital space allows for a more conversational tone, mirroring the immediacy and interactivity inherent to these platforms. While this informality can enhance relatability and engagement, it also poses risks of misinterpretation and the spread of misinformation. The participatory nature of online media democratizes content creation, yet it

challenges traditional norms of speech culture, necessitating a vigilant approach to language use to maintain credibility and respectfulness in discourse.

Across these varied media formats, the core principles of speech culture — respect, integrity, and clarity — remain paramount. However, the application of these principles is tailored to fit the unique demands and opportunities of each medium, reflecting the evolving landscape of media communication and its enduring impact on public discourse.

In conclusion, the significance of speech culture in media discourse lies in its ability to shape perceptions, promote understanding, and contribute to a more cohesive and informed society. By prioritizing ethical communication practices and embracing diversity of voices, media outlets can fulfill their role as agents of positive social change. The exploration of speech culture within media discourse reveals its profound impact on how messages are crafted, delivered, and received. As media continues to evolve, the principles of speech culture remain a constant, guiding force, ensuring that communication remains respectful, effective, and reflective of societal values. In fostering a healthy speech culture, media professionals and consumers alike contribute to a discourse that enriches public dialogue and upholds the integrity of our collective conversations.

Moreover, the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning into media production and dissemination poses new considerations for speech culture. These technologies offer the potential to enhance content personalization and accessibility but also risk amplifying biases and misinformation if not carefully managed. As such, future developments in speech culture will likely involve ethical guidelines and regulatory frameworks that address these emerging technologies, ensuring they serve to enrich public discourse rather than detract from it.

Ultimately, the future of speech culture in media will depend on our collective ability to adapt to technological advancements while upholding the principles of respect, integrity, and inclusivity. By embracing innovation and fostering a culture of ethical communication, we can ensure that media continues to play a vital role in shaping an informed, engaged, and respectful society.

REFERENCES

1. Dobrosklonskaya T. *Medialinguistics: Systematic Approach to Language Styling* - Moscow: Flinta, 2008 - 203 p
2. Dobrosklonskaya T. G. In the Russian academic discourse "Extralinguistic means not pertaining to a language". 2014
3. Volkovo T. *Discourse Communicative Model of Translation: Monograph*. - Moscow: Flinta, 2010 - 125 p
4. Praeger: Silverblatt, A. *Media Literacy: Keys to Interpreting Media Messages*.
5. Pinker S., *Mind over mass media*, 2010.
6. Praeger S., *Media Literacy: Keys to Interpreting Media Messages*